

MODEL OF THE MOST CASES PROCESS IN BIOGAS DEVICES

Sh.J.Imomov¹

M.Q.Xoliqova¹

Z.J.Ergashov¹

*Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers" National Research university.
Bukhara City. Gazli ave. 32. 200100. Uzbekistan.*

zuxriddin72@mail.ru

Annotation: *In this paper, a model of multi-state processes (temperature, mixing, pH, degree of decomposition of organic waste, daily loading) in biogas plants were constructed. In the mathematical modeling of the process in biogas plants, the relationship between the interconnected elements is given separately. The quantitative level of generalization of each working part of the biogas plant is a clear formula that describes the number of parts in the system. In addition, the system under study is expressed using the first global mathematical model of the hierarchy, followed by the derivation of the model of the local part of the system from the original macromodel to the structure of the hierarchy.*

Keywords: *process, biogas, model, degree, raw material, degree of concentration, flow, coefficient, algorithm, system, modeling, correlation*

1 Introduction

Systematic nature of the anaerobic process in biogas plants [1,2,3,4] modeling indicates (temperature, mixing, pH, degree of decomposition of organic waste, daily loading, duration process and etc) the complexity of showing that it has not been seen in biogas production [5,6,7]. This process needs to be continued until small and precise systems are obtained that are not difficult to model. Such other indivisible subsystems are called elements of a complex system [8,9,11,12].

2 Materials and Methods

In our experiments, the biomass in the bioreactors was designed for step-by-step processing, and three bimas were loaded in advance (Picture 1). Organic waste is collected from the piggery and loaded into the primary treatment plant. The organic waste moisture, pH, chemical oxygen demand, volatile fatty acids and temperature regimes were controlled [5,6,10].

In constructing a mathematical model of the above process, the relationship between the interconnected elements plays an important role, i.e., the temperature depends on the rate of biomass loading or the duration of the process [12].

The mathematical model of a complex multilevel system consists of mathematical models of elements, structural analysis, and the relationship between them in terms of element speed or process duration [13,14].

The division into part systems is continued until simple part systems are obtained. That is, the mathematical expression of these part systems should not be complicated. These part systems, which have no other fragmentation ability, are

called elements of a complex system. When choosing a mathematical apparatus for modeling such elements, it is important that the elements of a given system class and the relationship between them.

Picture1. Biogas device for processing organic waste from piggery

It can be seen that the creation of mathematical models of optimization of multi-stage process control is also complicated by the fact that there are control systems in which optimal models operate, and multi-stage system processes are continuous and discrete.

In addition, the processes of a multi-state system are continuous and intermittent in nature, and most of these processes are non-linear.

3 Results and Discussion

In general, the diversity of management problems requires the construction of a multi-level system. requires the configuration of the parent system. The construction of the optimal model component of the problem depends on the periodicity of control and the frequency of correction of the models [15,16,17]. In the form of a hierarchical model, we can say that a multi-state technological process includes models structured for all instances of the control system.

The composition of this system model depends on the degree of integration of technological areas and the subsystems in each part of the system [23,24,25]. The quantitative degree of generalization of each working part of a biogas plant describes the number of parts in the system. In this case, the degree of concentration is determined by the following expression:

$$S = k_s * m^{-1},$$

Here m is the number of component systems involved in the construction of the integrated macromodel; k_s - a coefficient representing the structural properties of the system.

The mathematical model of the anaerobic process in biogas plants consists of a system of equations for a separate local part system and contours, which includes mathematical expressions of technological processes that represent the connections between them.

For each contour of this system, depending on the raw material to be processed and its quality, the material balance law is fulfilled in relation to the total product and its components.

From a mathematical point of view, the balance calculation of the scheme is brought to the solution of a system of algebraic equations. The following balance equations can be constructed for the contour of each scheme according to the mass of the product:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{k_{i1}} \gamma_{is}^{bx} = \sum_{s=k_{i2}+1}^{k_{i2}} \gamma_{is}^{b_{i1}x}, \quad i = \overline{1, n}; \quad s = \overline{1, n_{i1} + n_{i2}} \quad (1.1)$$

and by mass of components:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{k_{i1}} \gamma_{is}^{bx} d_{ijs}^{bx} = \sum_{s=k_{i2}+1}^{k_{i2}} \gamma_{is}^{b_{i1}x} d_{ijs}^{b_{i1}x}, \quad j = \overline{1, m}. \quad (1.2)$$

Here - contour number, number of contours, m - number of components, s - contour product number, - number of inputs and outputs. $ik - k_{i1}k_{i2}$

It should be noted that the solution of the knee of equilibrium equations has a number of computational difficulties: the size of the system measurements, poorly justified, uncertainty, inconsistency and flammability of ore beneficiation schemes. The modern technological scheme of processing of raw materials does not take place without the return of circulating products, ie the product from the following circuits must be sent to the beginning of the scheme for processing. However, the full characteristics of the product must be taken into account when calculating the circuit contour balance. It is necessary to use balance equations and more complex equations.

In the second stage, mathematical models are constructed for each separated contour, taking into account the constraints and limitations, based on the results of the first stage.

We consider the process of creating an integrated macromodel of the anaerobic multistage process in biogas plants [18,19,20]. The following material balance equations are appropriate for the u-contour of the multistage process in biogas plants:

$$\alpha_i \gamma_{\alpha_i} = \beta \gamma_i + \theta_i \gamma_{\theta_i}, \quad (1.3)$$

$$\gamma_{\alpha_i} = \gamma_{\beta_i} + \gamma_{\theta_i}, \quad (1.4)$$

Here, the amount of useful metal in the concentrate consumed in biogas plants and i - the amount of useful metal in the waste products of the contour; i is the amount of solids in the concentrate and waste products consumed by the contour. $\alpha_i, \beta_i, \theta_i - \gamma_{\alpha_i} \gamma_{\beta_i} \gamma_{\theta_i} -$

Currents from other circuits and the initial current may come to the input of the contour. As a result, we get:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{\pi} (\omega_{ij} \beta_j \gamma_{\beta_j} + \kappa_{ij} \theta_j \gamma_{\theta_j}) + \alpha_i^0 \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0}{\sum_{j=1}^{\pi} (\omega_{ij} \gamma_{\beta_j} + \kappa_{ij} \gamma_{\theta_j}) + \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0}, \quad (1.5)$$

$$\gamma_{\alpha_i} = \sum_{j=1}^{\pi} (\omega_{ij} \gamma_{\beta_j} + \kappa_{ij} \gamma_{\theta_j}) + \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0 \quad (1.6)$$

Here

ω_{ij} = presence of a useful metal in the initial flow; α_i^0 –

solid output in the initial current. $\gamma_{\alpha_i}^0$ –

i – By changing equations from 1 to n (1.5), (1.6), we create a system of linear algebraic equations using equations, and by solving this system we find the functions:

$$\gamma_{\beta_i} = \gamma_{\beta_i}(\alpha_1^0, \alpha_2^0, \dots, \alpha_n^0, \gamma_{\alpha_1}^0, \gamma_{\alpha_2}^0, \dots, \gamma_{\alpha_n}^0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n, \theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n),$$

$$\gamma_{\theta_i} = \gamma_{\theta_i}(\alpha_1^0, \alpha_2^0, \dots, \alpha_n^0, \gamma_{\alpha_1}^0, \gamma_{\alpha_2}^0, \dots, \gamma_{\alpha_n}^0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n, \theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n),$$

In this case, i varies from 1 to n

$i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

If β_{π} represents the amount of useful metal in the finished product, then the system of equations is determined from the state of material balance according to the following technological scheme: $\beta_{\pi} \gamma_{\beta_{\pi}}$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\pi} \alpha_i^0 \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0 = \beta_{\pi} \gamma_{\beta_{\pi}} + \theta_{omb} \gamma_{\theta_{omb}}, \quad (1.7)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\pi} \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0 = \gamma_{\beta_{\pi}} + \gamma_{\theta_{omb}}. \quad (1.8)$$

From this system we create a macromodel to determine the amount of useful metal in the waste products:

$$\theta_{omb} = \beta_{\pi} - \frac{\beta_{\pi} \sum_{i=1}^{\pi} \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0 - \sum_{i=1}^{\pi} \alpha_i^0 \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0}{\sum_{i=1}^{\pi} \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0 - \gamma_{\beta_{\pi}}}. \quad (1.9)$$

The macromodel has the following appearance in relation to the amount of useful metal in the finished concentrate:

$$\beta_{\pi} = \theta_{omb} - \frac{\theta_{omb} \gamma_{\theta_{omb}} - \sum_{i=1}^{\pi} \alpha_i^0 \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0}{\gamma_{\beta_{\pi}}}. \quad (1.10)$$

The extraction of a useful metal from a similar finished concentrate is determined as follows:

$$\varepsilon = \beta_{\pi} \gamma_{\beta_{\pi}} / \sum_{i=1}^{\pi} \alpha_i^0 \gamma_{\alpha_i}^0. \quad (1.11)$$

Thus, in the initial stage of modeling, a macromodel is created for the whole process using only the input and output parameters of the contours.

4 Conclusion

Hence, in the second stage, a macromodel is created for the local part systems of the multi-state technological process.

The studied hierarchy of the system is represented using the first global mathematical model. Micromodels of local part systems are then derived from the original macromodel using the hierarchy structure. Thus, the problem leads to finding the optimal solution of the initial mathematical model. The results obtained using different methodologies are then compared and the best method that meets the defined criteria is selected. In this case, the high-level model is built taking into account the conditionally optimal solutions of low-level micromodels. In turn, the solution found using the higher-level macromodel is sent to the lower-level model, and a detailed solution is sought in that model.

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